

Water-Controlled 1-bit Reconfigurable Surface

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Abstract — In this paper, a reconfigurable surface (RS) is demonstrated using water in microfluidic channels as the control elements. The pattern reconfigurability is achieved through selectively filling the channels in an array with water. Different from conventional electronic-based RSs where the tuning elements are placed on the reflective elements, the phase change in the proposed design is induced by switching the states of the defected ground plane by using water to load or unload a ring slot structure. This approach minimizes the adverse impact of the tuning elements and the associated actuation mechanism on the RF performance of the reconfigurable metasurfaces. The capability of the 1-bit RS to generate multi-beam deflection patterns at 14.45 GHz is demonstrated. Both a broadside pattern and a two-beam reflection at 10° are shown. The measured results verify the multi-beam reflections at 14.45 GHz. Additionally, the proposed RS achieves a measured broadside gain of 6.82 dBi.

Keywords — reconfigurable surface, metasurface.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable Surfaces (RS) are essential for enhancing signal propagation and network performance in wireless communications. Created from unit cells, these surfaces dynamically alter their electromagnetic properties to manipulate incident waves. Traditionally, electronic components such as PIN diodes [1], [2] and varactors [3], [4] enable reconfigurability by altering phase states to control reflection responses. However, their low-quality factors can degrade system performance. Additionally, PIN diode-based RIS provides limited phase shifts, while varactor-based RIS introduces significant magnitude variations. Mechanically reconfigurable surfaces [5] adjust electromagnetic responses using motors to reshape unit cells, offering reliability but suffering from bulkiness and slow response. In contrast, CMOS technology [6] enables miniaturization, integration, and high-speed operation but faces challenges such as complex fabrication and limited phase-tuning at high frequencies. MEMS [7] operate at the micro- or nanoscale, adjusting mechanical structures in response to external stimuli. They offer high energy efficiency, making them ideal for low-power applications, but are limited by complex fabrication and slow switching speeds. To address these issues, researchers explore phase-changing materials such as liquid crystals [8], vanadium dioxide [9], Germanium-Antimony-Tellurium (Ge₂Sb₂Te₅, or GST) [10], and graphene [11], which dynamically modify electromagnetic properties. However, their use presents challenges in fabrication and reliability, especially when thermal or optical control mechanisms are involved. This paper introduces a novel reconfigurable reflective metasurface utilizing fluidic channels beneath a slotted-ground plane. The proposed water-controlled

reconfigurable surface achieves phase modulation by adjusting water movement within microfluidic channels. Water, as a material with considerable conductivity, can load and unload the ring slot, creating two distinct states that influence amplitude and phase response of the unit cell. Unlike conventional approaches that integrate phase-changing elements on the unit cell surface or within the substrate, this design reduces unwanted scattering by isolating the phase-switching medium from the illuminated waves. In [12], the authors proposed a water-based metasurface, but the water channels were integrated into the unit cell substrate, which can lead to higher electromagnetic losses, reduced mechanical stability, and more complex fabrication due to direct interaction with the electromagnetic fields. In contrast, the use of water channels behind the ground plane, as introduced in this paper, decouples the tuning function from the radiation structure. This fluid-based reconfiguration mechanism offers a flexible and scalable alternative for RS development, balancing electronic and mechanical approaches. It reduces design complexity compared to electronic methods while achieving a better response time than mechanical systems. Integrating fluidic channels in RS offers distinct advantages. Water movement can be controlled using pumps, enabling high reconfigurability. Moreover, the symmetrical unit cell design and placement of the phase-changing element beneath the ground plane ensure polarization independence.

II. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The proposed design, shown in Fig. 1, consists of a metasurface on a PCB and a PDMS (polydimethylsiloxane) layer that holds the channels. PDMS, with a dielectric constant approximately 2.67, is known for its high elasticity and low of surface energy. The unit cell of the designed RS is depicted in Fig. 2 and is composed of multiple layers. These include the crossed dipoles as the top patch, a Taconic RF-60TC substrate ($\epsilon_r = 6.15$, $\tan\delta = 0.002$), a ground plane featuring a square ring slot, and a very thin PDMS layer spin-coated onto the ground plane. Beneath the slot, a PDMS fluidic channel is positioned. The phase shift in the proposed design is triggered by changing the state of the defected ground plane, utilizing water to either fill or empty the ring slot structure. In this paper, water, with a dielectric constant of approximately 50.83 and a conductivity of 29.30 S/m within the 14–15 GHz frequency range [13], is utilized. The conductivity of water is calculated using the following equation [14]:

$$\sigma = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'' \quad (1)$$

Where, ω is the angular frequency, ϵ_0 denotes permittivity of free space and ϵ'' is the imaginary part of the complex permittivity, normally referred to as the loss index.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Proposed RS: (a) Overall view; (b) Bottom view with schematic of channels and slots; (c) Bottom view including PDMS with inlets and outlets. Dimensions: $L_r=90$ mm

Fig. 2. Proposed fluidic unit cell structure: (a) Overall view; (b) View of the slot in the ground plane. Dimensions in mm: $L_u=5$, $W_p=1$, $L_p=3.87$, $S_p=1.435$, $H_s=0.64$, $H_p=5$, $H_c=2$, $W_c=2.44$, $L_s=1.82$, $L_{sg}=1.4$

Fig. 3. Unit cell reflection coefficient responses: (a) Magnitude; (b) Phase

The complex permittivity of water can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - j\epsilon'' \quad (2)$$

Where the ϵ' electrical permittivity. A table containing the real and imaginary parts of water complex permittivity at 25°C across different frequencies is provided in reference [13]. In

this paper, the emphasis is on utilizing water as a medium to alter the state of the ring slot within the defected ground plane, resulting in a 180° phase shift between the two states at the target frequency of 14.45 GHz, as demonstrated in the simulation results in Fig. 3b. The simulations were carried out using CST Microwave Studio under unit cell boundary conditions. This 180° phase difference fulfills the 1-bit reconfigurability requirement, enabling deflected patterns such as single-beam and two-beam. Compared to the empty channels, however, the lossy water causes significant absorption, resulting in a reflection magnitude of -9 dB (Fig. 3a). To better clarify the water impact on the unit cell responses, water with different dielectric constants and conductivities are considered. Fig. 4 demonstrates the amplitude and phase responses of the proposed unit cell for different dielectric constants of water while keeping the conductivity constant at 29.3 S/m. Fig. 5 illustrates the amplitude and phase responses of the proposed unit cell for

Fig. 4. Unit cell responses for different dielectric constants: (a) Magnitude; (b) Phase

different conductivities while maintaining a stable dielectric constant of 50.83. It can be observed that increasing the dielectric constant, raises the magnitude of the unit cell response, moving it closer to zero (Fig. 4a). However, increasing the conductivity, decreases the reflection magnitude of the unit cell at higher frequencies (Fig. 5a). Additionally, from the phase responses, it can be seen that increasing both the dielectric constant and conductivity, shifts the maximum phase (180°) and corresponding resonant to higher frequencies (Fig. 4b and Fig. 5b). An $M \times N$ array produces a scattering pattern as expressed [15]:

$$E(\theta, \varphi) = EP(\theta, \varphi) \cdot AF(\theta, \varphi) \quad (3)$$

where θ and φ are the elevation and azimuth angles, and EP is the reflection amplitude of each cell. For normal incidence, the array factor (AF) can be represented by Equation (4):

$$AF(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \exp \left\{ jkd \left[\left(m - \frac{1}{2} \right) \cdot \sin \theta \cos \varphi - \left(n - \frac{1}{2} \right) \cdot \sin \theta \sin \varphi + j\phi(m, n) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

Here, M and N are the number of elements along the x - and y -axes, k is the wave number and d is the unit cell size. The phase term $j\phi(m, n)$ controls the reflection direction. In proposed design, to enable reconfigurability on a fixed metasurface, fluidic channels are integrated, allowing dynamic switching of the phase states in PCB-based unit cells. In this work, a 16×16 unit cell array is employed. Fig. 6 illustrates the specular and multi-beam anomalous reflections of the RS under normal incident wave, with only the fluidic channels shown for clarity. Specular or mirror type reflection at broadside occurs when all channels are either empty or filled with water, with the empty state depicted in Fig. 6a. Anomalous reflections could produce a two-beam pattern at 10° (Fig. 6b), where channels are partially filled, with one half containing water and the other half filled with air.

Fig. 5. Unit cell responses for different conductivities: (a) Magnitude; (b) Phase

Fig. 6. Simulated patterns of the water based RS: (a) Specular reflection; (b) Two-beam anomalous reflection

III. FABRICATION AND MEASUREMENT

A 16×16 unit cells prototype of the RS has been fabricated, combining a metasurface on a PCB (Fig. 7a) with PDMS fluidic channels (Fig. 7b). This PDMS substrate have been used to hold fluidic channels and are attached to the PCB using a plasma bonding technique. To reinforce adhesion, a thin PDMS layer was first spin-coated onto the PCB ground plane before bonding. A syringe pump is employed to control the injection and withdrawal of water within the channels. The measurement setup comprises a transmitting antenna (TX Horn), a receiving antenna (RX Horn), and a vector network analyser. The TX Horn is connected to the transmitting port of the VNA, while the RX Horn is linked to the receiving port. The RS is positioned in the far-field region of the TX Horn, and the RX Horn is placed in the far-field region of the RS. Both the RS and TX Horn are securely mounted on the rotation system, ensuring continuous illumination by the incident wave throughout the rotation. To minimize the shielding effect during the 0° measurement, the RX horn is positioned slightly above the TX horn. Fig. 8 depicts the radiation patterns and gain of the proposed RS observed in both measurement and simulation. Specifically, Fig. 8a illustrates the specular reflection state of the RS when the channels are empty (Fig. 6a), resulting in a broadside reflected beam at 0° . In this state, the RS reflects the incident wave at the same angle at which it illuminates. Fig. 8b illustrates the two-beam pattern scenario with reflections at $\pm 10^\circ$, where half of the channels are filled with water while the other half remain empty, as shown in Fig. 6b. In both reflection scenarios—particularly in the normal reflection case—there is good agreement between simulation and measurement at the target directions (0° for normal reflection and $\pm 10^\circ$ for dual-beam reflection); however, slight discrepancies in sidelobe levels are observed, likely caused by residual shielding effects, alignment inaccuracies, or environmental reflections. Fig. 8c represents the measured gain of the proposed RS under normal illumination, comparing it with simulation results. The main beam achieves a measured gain of 6.82 dBi, which is relatively low due to the RS small size and the inherently lossy nature of water. The small difference between simulated and measured gain is due to changes in dielectric properties in comparison with ideal simulation conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study integrates water into the unit cells of the RS to enable reconfigurability. By leveraging water and air, a 180°

Fig. 7. Fabricated RS: (a) Front view; (b) Back view comprising PDMS and channels.

Fig. 8. Measured and simulated patterns for different configurations of the channels: (a) Broadside pattern for all channels filled with air; (b) Two-beam pattern utilizing water and air configuration; (c) Far-field broadside simulated and measured gain of RS at 14.45 GHz

phase shift between the two states within each unit cell is achieved, allowing for adaptable deflected radiation patterns. The feasibility of the 1-bit RS in generating a broadside pattern, and two-beam reflection at 14.45 GHz is successfully demonstrated and confirmed experimentally. Additionally, the proposed RS achieves a measured broadside gain of 6.82 dBi.

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